

Effect of azolla inoculation on rice yield, Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			Increase (%)
	1978-79 kharif	1979-80 kharif	1979-80 rabi	
Control	1.7	2.1	3.5	-
Azolla at 10 t/ha	2.1	3.0	4.6	34
Azolla at 1 t/ha, surface applied	1.9	2.6	4.2	20
Azolla at 5 t/ha + 15 kg N/ha	2.0	3.0	4.3	30
30 kg N/ha	2.1	3.0	4.6	34
60 kg N/ha	2.3	3.5	4.6	44
CD	0.4	0.6	0.6	

produced the same yield as 30 kg N/ ha. Highest yields were with azolla + urea. Applying azolla increased both total and available N. With 8 azolla crops in 1 season, total N harvest was about 140 kg/ ha at Bhubaneswar and 80 kg] ha in saline conditions. *ℒ*

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Effect of phosphorus on kharif rice

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We determined the P requirement of kharif rices in 1984 on soil with pH 7.8, EC 0.70 mmho/crn, 0.68% organic carbon, and 12.1 kg available P and 329 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. P at 0, 8.7, 17.5, and 26.2 kg/ ha applied basally as superphosphate were main plots; Swarna, Lakshmi, MTU7633, and Vasista were subplots. NK at 40-30 kg/ ha were applied to all treatments.

Swarna yielded highest with an average 5.3 t/ha, which was significantly

Grain and straw yields of 4 rices at 4 P levels, Maruteru, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Straw yield (t/ha)					
	0	8.7 kg	17.5 kg	26.2 kg	Mean	0	8.7 kg	17.5 kg	26.2 kg	Mean	
Swarna	5.1	5.2	5.4	5.5	5.3	6.1	5.9	6.2	6.2	6.1	
Lakshmi	4.0	3.8	4.1	4.3	4.1	5.0	5.0	4.9	5.1	5.0	
MTU7633	4.5	5.1	5.1	5.2	5.0	6.5	6.4	6.6	6.5	6.5	
Vasista	4.5	4.8	4.7	5.0	4.7	6.1	6.2	6.9	6.4	6.4	
Mean	4.5	4.7	4.8	5.0	4.8	5.9	5.9	6.2	6.0	6.0	
CD at 5%											
P levels						0.3	ns				
Varieties						0.2	0.2				
P levels × varieties						ns	ns				
Varieties × P levels						ns	ns				
CV%						4.8	3.7				

superior to that of all other varieties. P significantly increased yield only at 26.2 kg P/ ha (see table). P levels did not significantly influence straw yield.

MTU7633 had the highest mean straw yield of 6.5 t/ ha. Swarna performed best and 8.7 kg P/ha appears to be optimum and economical for the test varieties. *ℒ*

Storing Azolla pinnata inoculum for transport

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We evaluated different storage techniques for *A. pinnata*, Coimbatore strain. Fresh *A. pinnata* fronds were collected from field multiplication plots, soil was washed from their roots, and water was drained from them. The fronds were stored in cotton cloth, polyester cloth, newspaper, brown paper, polythene, polythene-lined gunny, and gunny bags for 5 d. Frond survival was recorded on days 2, 3, 4, and 5. All

Different bags for storing azolla, Coimbatore, India,

Treatment	Azolla survival (%)				Recovery (%) in the field when inoculated
	2d	3d	4d	5d	
Cotton cloth bag	100	58	45	19	26
Polyester cloth bag	100	53	40	17	17
Newspaper bag	100	57	56	19	21
Brown paper bag	100	41	38	16	15
Polythene bag	100	66	65	32	46
Polythene-lined gunny bag	100	62	46	28	27
Gunny bag	100	61	44	22	27
CD		5	5	2	4

azolla lived for 2 d, then began to die. At 5 d, polythene and polythene-lined

gunny bags performed best (see table). *ℒ*

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